

LEGAL SERVICES TO MENTALLY ILL AND MENTALLY DISABLED: A CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF THE GOVERNMENT SCHEMES

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ABSTRACT

Persons with disabilities, particularly those suffering from mental illness or who are intellectually retarded, are marginalized, and the study focused on the individual who need special protection from the state and, more significantly, society. The Mental Health Act of 1987 and the National Trust for the Welfare of Persons with Autism, Cerebral Palsy, Mental Retardation, and Multiple Disabilities Act of 1999 are two pieces of legislation. India is also a signatory to the UN Agreement on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD) and one of the countries that has ratified the convention, making it our legal system's responsibility to protect the human rights and fundamental liberties of people with disabilities. The Legal Services Authorities Act of 1978 and the NALSA (Legal Services to the Mentally Ill and Mentally Disabled Persons) Scheme of 2015 provide for the provision of legal services to the mentally ill and mentally disabled. These legal services are offered to patients in psychiatric hospitals, homes, and facilities by lawyers who have been trained to advocate the best interests of mentally ill people. Organizing awareness initiatives in distant areas of the country to educate people that mental illness is curable and that they must be treated equally with other members of society is one of the scheme's various objectives. As a result, in this study, the researcher has attempted to critically assess the schemes that have been developed through various statutes adopted for the benefit of mentally ill persons, as well as their impact on society and its evolution over time.

Keywords

Mental, illness, Autism, disability, Mental Health Act 1987, National Trust for the Welfare of Persons with Autism, Cerebral Palsy, Mental Retardation and Multiple Disabilities Act, 1999.

HYPOTHESIS

The researcher strongly believes that the government was expected not only to draught the policy for specially challenged people but also to monitor it. There is a need to restore the confidence of mentally sick and mentally impaired people, which has been shattered as a result of the difficulties they confront on a daily basis. Their social position would significantly improve if they were economically boosted.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Both doctrinal and empirical methods were used as the research methodology. Therefore, information has been gathered from several articles, newspapers, and other sources. Snowball sampling was being opted as the study's sample method.

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INTRODUCTION

“A genius is a mentally ill person with an audience “¹

It is especially required to know a few terms previously going to the target of this research paper. Terms like psychological instability and rationally a few people in their nearby dialect to deride or insult somebody are utilizing impeded however whether the word basically utilized as a part of the individual who makes utilization of it comprehends easygoing way. Do other individuals think about the significance of these words and its profundity? It is a genuine inquiry, which additionally attempts to draw out the reaction of the general public toward the rationally sick and rationally hindered individuals. Let's go through the various definitions which is being provided by the various institution one of such definition are being provided by Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Government of India for Mental Health it states mental health is a state of well-being in which the individuals realize their own abilities, it also includes promotion of mental well-being and prevention of mental disorders. Mental health problem ranges from psych-asocial distress, mental illness affects a large number of people whereas mental disability affects comparatively to a small number of people. Schizophrenia, bipolar disorder, depression or obsessive-compulsive disorder is covered within the term mental illness. Mental disability refers to disability associated with mental illness; it is not necessary that all the person who has mental illness will also have the disability due the hindrance created by the society. The New Act would align our laws with the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UNCRPD), which India has ratified. As a result, India will be able to satisfy its UNCRD responsibilities. Furthermore, the new law would not only strengthen Divyangjan's rights and entitlements, but will also create an effective framework for ensuring their empowerment and full integration into society.²

Indian constitution has the characteristics of federal form of government in itself and the nation is governed by constitution, the union government and the state government of various states have a major responsibility for the promotion of mental health, treatment of mental illness and prevention of mental illness across length and breadth of the country. The government should bring players of private sectors

¹ Tim Minchin Quotes, < <https://quotefancy.com/quote/1541667/Tim-Minchin-A-genius-is-a-mentally-ill-person-with-an-audience#:~:text=Tim%20Minchin%20Quote%3A%20%E2%80%9CA%20genius,ill%20person%20with%20an%20audience.%E2%80%9D>> Accessed on 29th March 2022.

² Press Information Bureau, Government of India, Ministry of Social Justice & Empowerment 16-December-2016 18:28 IST, Rights of Persons with Disabilities Bill - 2016 Passed by Parliament <<http://pib.nic.in/newsite/PrintRelease.aspx?relid=155592>>(Last Open 10/10/17, 04:30 pm)

and government sectors such as private care contributors, non-governmental organization and various groups' governmental hospital and care providers to make synchronized efforts with the utmost interest to help mentally ill and mentally disabled people.

The government should release adequate funds to meet the various aims of the government, which is being depicted in National Mental Health Policy. Financial support should be extended to government hospitals and community based to rehabilitation center, as it will be major step in the direction of positive progress of achievement of government scheme's. The research paper mainly analyzes the various government schemes and policy of union government and various state governments and what is the progress of programs and various methods to achieve the objective of schemes. The UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UNCRPD) has considerably boosted the visibility and reinforcement of disability rights around the world since its ratification and entry into effect.³ India was one of the first countries to join the UNCRPD, although it has yet to adopt the Convention's provisions into its domestic laws.⁴

NATIONAL LEGAL SERVICES AUTHORITY (LEGAL SERVICES TO THE MENTALLY ILL PERSONS AND PERSONS WITH MENTAL DISABILITIES) SCHEME, 2010

The United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UNCRPD) is a treaty that India is a signatory to. (CRPD).⁵ All countries are required to incorporate the Convention's substantive rights and principles into their national legislation⁶. UN convention on the rights of persons with disabilities (CRPD) 2008 is considered one of the significant International legal frameworks for the benefit for the people suffering from mental illness and mental disabilities. India being signatory to this convention has obligation to ensure the people with the disability are exercising the Human Rights. The convention is the result of basic understanding of big think tank that access to justice to mentally ill and disable is achieved with a lot of hardship therefore the convention ensures creation of accessible justice with effective and on equal basis. In India the attitude of the state has always been one of charity and welfare. Schools and residential institutions primarily for visually and orthopedically impaired people were established in cities with religious shrines (such as Benares and Lucknow), where there was a

³ United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UNCRPD), <<https://humanrights.gov.au/our-work/disability-rights/united-nations-convention-rights-persons-disabilities-uncrpd>> Accessed 23rd march 2022

⁴ Rights of Persons with Disability in India, Dr. Rumi Ahmed, White Falcon Publishing Solutions Llp, 2015.

⁵ Sampurnaa Dutta, Discrimination Generated By the Intersection of Gender and Disability, IOSR Journal of Dental and Medical Sciences Volume 14, 35 DOI: 10.9790/0853-14663336 (2015)

⁶ Centre for Legislative research and advocacy, CLRA Policy Brief for Parliamentarians, Indian Disability Laws- an obsolete picture, policy brief series: No. 5; 2008 August

plethora of disabled people living off the donation of visiting pilgrims, beginning during the colonial period.⁷

The scheme is going to be enforced by legal service institution such as Supreme Court legal services committee, state legal service authorities District level service authorities, Taluk Legal Service Authorities. The scheme is consisting of 2 parts first part enshrining guideline, which is to be followed by the legal service institution. Telling Mental illness is curable and it should be kept in mind before rendering services. The dignity is to be respected by the institution as well as ensuring the fundamental freedom is provided at the same time. The scheme clearly provides guidelines that there should be no discrimination based on the mental illness the person has. The right behavior and attitude is to be ensured, one of the particular thing is be kept in mind by the institution is that getting treatment is fundamental right of mentally ill people under Article 21 of the Constitution if they are deprived of this particular then the course of law mentioned under chapter IV is to be invoked. Informed consent as per provided by Mental Health Act 2017, which is basically permission to intervene with the consent without influence, fraud, threat, mistake or misrepresentation, the same consent is required to provide help to mentally ill people therefore consent is one of the significant factors to treat a person with illness other than mentally ill people also. If the mentally ill people is not able to provide the informed consent is to be taken by his/her relative or friend and if exception exist if relative and friend is not there the court could provide the permission to treat mentally ill people. In 2017 the Supreme Court of India uphold Right to Privacy as Fundamental Right therefore this particular right should be ensured along with dignity to mentally ill people without and discrimination.

The 2006 National Policy for Persons with Disabilities emphasizes the importance of applying the Constitutional vision to people with disabilities. The Policy suggests changes to existing laws that affect people with disabilities.⁸ The scheme provides provision for the legal services institution to visit the various places such as psychiatric hospitals or psychiatric nursing homes and other places where mentally ill people were confined, the institution should also gather information regarding the confine, all the information regarding the hardship is faced by the mentally ill people the method of obtaining information would be also simple such as interviewing the authority managing the hospitals or places like such interviewing the mentally ill people. The information should be used to ensure the rights to the mentally ill people. Legal service institution also has the local jurisdiction to keep note of all the judgments, which is being passed by the court in the matter in which, mentally ill person is one of the party and also keep treatment report within the record of institution and also bring to the notice of the

7, Nandini Ghosh, Dynamics of Asian Development, Interrogating Disability in India: Theory and Practice, (Springer Publications, 2015)

⁸ Kalpana Kannibrian, NALSAR University Faculty Of Law, Monitoring The Human Rights Of Persons With Disabilities: Law, Policies And Programs In India Copyright 2009 Disability Rights Promotion International (D.R.P.I.) (Page No. 5), 2009

Magistrate about the progress of report. Legal services would also be provided to those mentally ill people who are forcefully being admitted to the psychiatric hospitals or psychiatric nursing. Legal services institutions should in cooperation with district legal services authorities regarding the matter of judicial inquisition and management of the property of mentally ill person. Mental health act also provides for the provision Legal services coming across any information regarding misappropriation or fraudulent property of mentally ill person the authority will bring the incident into the mind of District Legal Service Authority.

One of the most significant entitlement is being done by Section 27 “**A person with mental illness shall be entitled to receive free legal services to exercise any of his rights given under this Act**”⁹ of Mental Health Act, 2017 provide the free legal services provision if she/he is need of it. Therefore, the legal services authority is having obligation to provide help to mentally ill people and ensure that rights is being exercised as per given by this act and constitution of India. The best way to educate mentally ill people is to teach their relatives and friends about the rights that they are entitled to under the law. However, it could also be done by organizing various legal programs to raise awareness of the condition that mentally ill people are in and what can be done to help them overcome the stigma created by today's society. However, the first change that could be made is to change people's mindset. Various camps, organized by psychiatric institutions and attended by members of the legal services authority, could assist in educating social workers, lawyers, and relatives of mentally ill persons, as well as dispelling stigmas and misconceptions regarding mental illness. To ensure that mentally ill people receive justice, the judiciary must play a key role. As a result, awareness programs should be extended to judicial officers and panel lawyers, as well as the respective state bar association in that state, to provide enough knowledge to better understand the situation of mentally ill people and to sensitize them about the socio-legal hardships they face. Lower-level authorities, such as the state legal services authority and the district legal services authority, should try to rehabilitate mentally ill people once they have been cured, the humanitarian situation should be ensured, and the legal services authority should make a proper visit to see if proper medication, food, and medication has been done. Because of their condition, many people with disabilities are refused equitable access to healthcare, education, work prospects, or political involvement (World Health Organization and World Bank, 2011), jeopardizing their social inclusion. Disability is a development issue as well, with a growing body of evidence demonstrating that people with disabilities have worse socioeconomic results and are more likely to be poor than people without disabilities. (MacLachlan and Swartz, 2009; United Nations, 2011).¹⁰

STATE LEGAL SERVICE AUTHORITY AND JAIL

⁹ Mental Healthcare Act, 2017 § 27

¹⁰ Khaled Nasser, Malcolm MacLachlan, Joanne McVeigh, Social Inclusion and Mental Health of Children with Physical Disabilities in Gaza, Palestine, Disability, CBR and Inclusive Development, Volume 27, No. 4, 2016

The supreme court of India in the case of *Sheela Barse Vs. Union Of India*¹¹, criticized the practice of keeping mentally disabled people and held that this practice is illegal and unconstitutional, after this the Supreme court directed that Judicial Magistrate after attaining proper advice of professional or psychiatrist regarding the mentally ill person shall sent the person to safe custody for treatment and also provide quarterly reports to the High Courts the respective state. In the respective case to meet the standards set up by Supreme Court the following things were to be required, It will be the responsibility of State services legal Authority to ensure the whether if any Mentally disabled person is in jail he/she should be immediately shifted to appropriate place and also take required steps for the treatment of that person, this provision is to be started only the permission is being obtained by the High court and work will be done along with the help of State Mental Health Authority. Judicial magistrate will send quarterly report to high court for the number of cases being entertained by respective and number of people in safe custody. The state services legal authority will also go through report and issue the guidelines for the district state legal service authority to conduct proper enquiry to know the whether the condition of the places where mentally ill people go are humane in condition also state legal services authority will bring in the attention of designated judges regarding the course of matter.

STATE LEGAL SERVICES AUTHORITY AND HOSPITALS, HOMES AND FACILITIES

State Legal services Authority shall advice High Court under section 37 of the act, to constitute board with member secretary and state legal service authority or district legal services authority to visit regularly to examine the condition of inmates in respective houses, facilities and hospitals. Also, the board should also take step for rehabilitation of the inmates one who is cured, if inmates are not able to contact their family required steps should be taken for the getting back into family, family sometimes denies to take back mentally ill person because of the stigma or even sometimes due to property issues state legal services authority along with the board try present the case before court to seek order for the restoration of the victim of family's negative step.

Mentally sound person through interaction can come to know about weather something wrong with the person mentally or not, when board visit such facilities try to interact with inmates along with the psychiatric to know whether person is genuinely mentally ill or is victim of forced admission by the family.

MENTALLY ILL AND MENTALLY DISABLED PEOPLE AND COURT PROCEEDINGS

Court proceeding in India is one of the most time taking actions, which take place in the course of getting justice. Mentally sound people find it tiring some job to take the matter to the court because of the procedure, cost and on top of it the amount of time it takes. Therefore, there are several procedure

¹¹ Criminal Petition No.237/1989

mentioned mental health act and also adopted by the honorable judiciary to help mentally ill and mentally disabled people. The legal services authority can make request to judiciary to give a notice regarding the order given by the judiciary for the reception and discharge. The legal services authority is required to maintain the list of the mentally ill people in their local jurisdiction against whom the order of reception is being passed by the court, the authority is also required to keep check of the mentally ill person's treatment going in the facility of psychiatric nursing homes and psychiatric hospitals where the person is being send as per the reception order.

There might be several circumstances where the person being cured in the facility and need to be discharged from the particular facility, legal services authority should bring into the notice of honorable court to such circumstances so the that judiciary passes suitable requisite order. Therefore, legal services authority should move application for the discharge, as no patient should live after they are cured and they should be discharged as soon as possible.

Person with mental disability and who are mentally ill have also inheritance rights of the property. And various financial property they could avail bank loans, mortgages and various other financial instruments. Therefore, it is the judiciary and its various pillars to make mentally ill people to aware them about the rights they possess; legal services authority under mentally disabled for obtaining all benefits under the persons with Disabilities (Equal Opportunities, Protection of Rights and Full Participation) Act, 1995 shall assist mentally disabled people to get their due rights.

OTHER SERVICES PROVIDED BY THE GOVERNMENT OF INDIA

There are several other facilities provided by the government of India, which is very significant to mentally ill and mentally disabled people, after the amount of discrimination they go through it is the responsibility of the government to support them through various financial assistance scheme. They could be divided into several different categories:

1. Travel concession

Railways one of the biggest and most important transportation facilities in India tries to provide help disabled people. The help comes in the form of concession, which is given to the disabled people in the way of concession on the ticket prices; along with the disabled person if anyone is assisting her/him would also be entitled with the concession on their concession. The concession would be available when the person will provide certificate obtained by the government regarding mental illness and mental disability. Therefore, the certificate is significant evidence to avail the free services through railways. Although the concession is not 100% it is up to 75%, which also depends on several conditions put up by Indian Railways.

2. **Scholarship**

Mentally disabled people are provided with scholarship of rupee 1000 in the case when mentally disabled child is being admitted to the special school and whose guardian's income doesn't not exceed 12000 Per annum, one of the criticisms of this scheme could be the cap which is put on parents' income to decide the scholarship is drastically very less and therefore it should be increased to considerably a larger amount which sounds practical enough as well.

3. **Educational facility:**

There should be government institute for the mentally disabled children to impart values as much as possible. Furthermore, the institute should also provide vocational training to such disabled children.

In state of Gujarat the faculty who try to learn how to teach mentally disabled children is having provision to get 75 rupees as incentive However, such small amount does not encourage the participation of people to understand the situation of mentally ill and mentally disabled children. Therefore, a strong incentive mechanism should be built to help these children. The government of Gujarat should recognize the necessity to raise the incentive level to a respectable sum in order to encourage more people to enroll in training programs and raise awareness of the conditions being faced by mentally ill and mentally disabled people, which will also help them to cure at better pace.

CONCLUSION

“Use the skills that I have got.

Do not focus on what I have not.

Of course, I am aware of my limitation.

Yet, I am a part of God's wonderful creation.”¹²

India's economy is transitioning into one of the largest in the world. However, due to lack of social and economic development, some sections of the nation are being left behind. The government of India is responsible for the overall development of the nation which would include the development of people from all social and economic strata as well as mentally ill and mentally disabled people who are denied an equal chance to showcase their talent in the modern world. It is obvious that these individuals require particular consideration from the judiciary, legislature, executive, and even the media.

To ensure that these sections are getting equal opportunity to exhibit themselves and to exercise their legal entitlements to fundamental and economical rights, the Central government has implemented

¹² William E. Lightbourne, < <https://bitsofpositivity.com/best-disability-quotes/>> Accessed 28th February 2022

several schemes and policies. The major disadvantage of these numerous government-implemented schemes is that they haven't kept an eye on how these schemes are being administered.

There is tremendous scope in the development of such schemes in order to make their approach more centric in the development and curing of mentally ill and mentally disabled people such as,

- The government could establish a website along with the online app portal through which relatives and friends of mentally ill and mentally disabled people could get aware of various schemes launched by government of India and state government. There should be link for uploading the application for several grievances which mentally ill and mentally disabled person is seeking for is seeking for.
- The government instead of providing cash grievances should help mentally ill and mentally disabled person to open bank account to directly transfer money for financial assistance along with it the access of account in case of examining the transaction record is to be to national legal services authority.
- The government should increase the incentive for the faculty training for teaching mentally ill and mentally disabled person. And it should be made mandatory for law school to conduct workshop for sensitization program. A specific syllabus should be prepared by bar council and enacted in law schools to adopt the subject and give opportunity to student to conduct studies and visit psychiatric hospital and clinic to understand the ground zero problem of mentally ill and mentally disabled person.
- National legal services authority and its other branches at lower level should be provided with hefty amount of fund to meet their expense when dealing with court proceeding in which mentally ill and mentally disabled person is party to the case.
- The transport facility in the cities and inter city transport facility should permit the tickets to mentally ill and mentally disabled people at concession rate.
- Several mentally disabled people are capable enough to do higher studied therefore the Universities should take this matter into consideration to support them.
- Whenever the matter related to mentally ill and mentally disabled person come to the court it should be heard by a different bench constituted just for hearing matter of mentally ill and mentally disabled person.
- Severe punishment provision should be made under IPC for the families and friends who try to hinder mentally ill and mentally disabled people to exercise the property rights, economical rights and fundamental rights.

Therefore, the government must not only draft several schemes for the welfare of these underprivileged sections of the society but also keep an eye on its implementation. The need to bridge the confidence level of mentally ill and mentally disabled person is crucial now more than ever. Due to the difficulties encountered by them on a daily, these people have lost faith and confidence in themselves. The social standing of disabled individuals would significantly improve if these parts are to be economically raised with the aid of government programs and contributions of the society.

REFERENCES

1. Press Information Bureau, Government of India, Ministry of Social Justice & Empowerment
2. Monitoring the Human Rights of Persons with Disabilities
3. Khaled Nasser, Malcolm MacLachlan, Joanne McVeigh, Social Inclusion and Mental Health of Children with Physical Disabilities in Gaza, Palestine, Disability, CBR and Inclusive Development, Volume 27, No. 4, 2016
4. Discrimination Generated By the Intersection of Gender and Disability, IOSR Journal of Dental and Medical Sciences Volume 14.
5. Criminal Petition No.237/1989

WEBLINKS

- (<https://pib.gov.in/newsite/PrintRelease.aspx?relid=155592>)
- <http://www.yorku.ca/drpi/files/IndiaLawsRep.pdf>